

PARAMETER STUDY OF SHORT CARBON FIBER REINFORCED CARBON

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Keywords: *Short fiber, Carbon fiber, CFRC, Parameter study*

1 Introduction

The use of carbon-carbon composites (C/Cs) is essential for many high temperature applications such as aircraft brakes, interior of furnaces or gratings for metal hardening. C/Cs are manufactured via several high temperature process steps, which are expensive and time consuming. But all industrial applications of C/Cs have to be economical. Therefore it is of great advantage to get an understanding about the properties of a C/C by measuring the properties of its greenbody state. Furthermore, the majority of all C/Cs applications are continuous fiber reinforced due to a lack of knowledge about the essential manufacturing parameters of short fiber C/Cs [1,2].

This paper describes a parameter study of fiber length, fiber surface, greenbody matrix material, and specimen thickness on the flexural strength (FS) and Young's modulus (YM) of short fiber C/Cs.

2 Experimental

The short fiber C/Cs plates were manufactured by mixing the PAN-based short carbon fibers and phenolic resin (novolak or resol). After mixing a hot molding process followed. The greenbodies were pyrolyzed at 1173 K in inert atmosphere. The carbonized greenbodies were densified by liquid impregnation of pitch with subjecting pyrolysis. After three densification cycles a graphitization at 2273 K in inert atmosphere was carried out. The short fiber C/Cs plates were cut into specimens of 6 mm x 8 mm x 100 mm (cf. Fig.1.) for 6 mm thick plates or 3 mm x 8 mm x 100 mm for 3 mm thin plates. This specimen geometries were chosen in dependence on DIN EN 658-3, DIN EN 843-1, ASTM C 11361, and ASTM C 1341.

Fig.1. Specimen geometry for 6 mm thick plates.

At least six specimens of greenbody state and final carbon-carbon (C/C) state were tested in a four point bending setup (cf. Fig.2.) with a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min to determine the FS. The YM was calculated with the secant method in the linear elastic region (10 % and 50 % of ultimate stress).

Fig.2. Four point bending test setup.

Parameters of fiber length were 3 mm and 6 mm. Three different fiber surfaces and fiber statuses were investigated. First, the virgin fibers with a seizing. Second the carbonized fibers, which were pyrolyzed at 1173 K in inert atmosphere. In this case the

seizing is destroyed thermally. The carbon fiber isn't modified at this temperature (1173 K) because of the higher heat treatment temperature (between 1573 K and 1673 K) in the high tenacity fiber production process [3]. The third configuration is graphitized fibers. By graphitization at 2273 K the seizing is thermally decomposed and high tenacity fibers are altered towards the properties of high modulus fibers [4]. Besides, novolak as precursor material for greenbody state one plate was prepared with a resol. The impact of the specimen thickness was studied with 3 mm and 6 mm thick samples.

3 Results and Discussion

The fiber volume fraction (V_f) achieved in all plates is between 47 % and 55 % in greenbody state. All measured FS and YM values were normalized to $V_f = 55$ % (cf. Fig.3. and Fig.4.). The nomenclature of the x-axis in Fig.3. and Fig.4. includes information of the fiber length; fiber surface and fiber status; greenbody matrix material; thickness of the short fiber C/Cs.

3.1 Flexural Strength

For both fiber lengths the thickness of the specimens has no significant influence on the measured FS. Within the 1st standard deviation the FS values are equal for greenbody as well as for C/C state (cf. Fig.3.). The deviation for the small cross section ($24 \text{ mm}^2 = 3 \text{ mm} \times 8 \text{ mm}$) is higher than for the big cross section ($48 \text{ mm}^2 = 6 \text{ mm} \times 8 \text{ mm}$). This independence of thickness is not self-evident, e.g. for tensile strength measurements of C/C-SiC with different cross sections a geometry dependence was reported [5].

3.1.1 Greenbody State

In the greenbody state, there is a decrease of FS observed if the seizing of the carbon fibers is decomposed. No difference is measurable between the carbonized and graphitized fibers. The fiber length has no influence on the FS. The sample with the resol precursor has the lowest FS values.

3.1.2 C/C State

In the C/C state, the sample with the resol precursor delaminated during graphitization. In the case of 3 mm fiber length the carbonized and virgin fiber's FS are equal. The graphitized fibers show less FS. If

6 mm long fibers are used, the carbonized fibers have the highest FS followed by the graphitized fibers. The virgin fibers have the lowest FS. For both lengths the carbonized fibers have higher FS than the graphitized ones which is in agreement with literature [3,4]. The increasing inhomogeneity of the plates with 6 mm long fibers [6] is causing lower FS values compared to the 3 mm fiber length. This effect is only observed for the weak carbon matrix and not for polymer matrix in the greenbody state.

3.1.3 Correlation of Greenbody and C/C State

Literature [7] reports an indirectional behavior for continuous reinforced C/Cs. The correlation coefficient between the greenbody and C/C state for the short fiber reinforced C/Cs in this study is 0.11.

Fig.3. FS values (normalized to $V_f = 55$ %) for greenbody and C/C state with the error bars indicating the 1st standard deviation.

This refers to neither a directional nor an indirectional behavior. A possible explanation is a superposition of the expected behavior by production fluctuation between the plates. For the minimization of this superposition, it is necessary to measure more specimens out of different plates for each parameter variation. By increasing the number of plates the statistical production fluctuation will be averaged.

3.2 Young’s Modulus

Also for the YM there is no difference between the thin and thick specimens observed.

3.2.1 Greenbody State

The behavior of YM for the greenbody state is the same as for the FS. Lower values are measured for fibers with decomposed seizing than with intact seizing. The carbonized and graphitized fibers are equal. YM values are not related to the fiber length within the 1st standard deviation. The resol precursor plate has the lowest YM of all samples.

3.2.2 C/C State

Due to delamination during graphitization of the resol precursor plate there are no YM values measured. The behavior of plates with 3 mm and 6 mm fiber length is different. In the case of 3 mm fibers, the thin and the thick plate with virgin fibers are equal (cf. Fig.4.: 1st and 2nd column). Also the thin plate with virgin fibers and the thick plate with carbonized fibers are equal (cf. Fig.4.: 1st and 3rd column), but the thick plate with virgin fibers and the thick plate with carbonized fibers have different YM (cf. Fig.4.: 2nd and 3rd column). For the thick plates only (cf. Fig.4.: 2nd, 3rd, and 4th column) the YM values in decreasing order are: plates with graphitized, virgin, and carbonized fibers. In the case of the 6 mm fibers the plates made out of virgin, carbonized, and graphitized fibers have the same YM. This different behavior has to be further investigated with more specimens per parameter variation to be able to neglect statistical effects.

3.1.3 Correlation of Greenbody and C/C State

As for the FS there is no strong correlation between the greenbody and C/C state. The correlation coefficient is 0.23. The main reason for this low coefficient maybe production fluctuations (see above).

Fig.4. YM values (normalized to $V_f = 55\%$) for greenbody and C/C state with the error bars indicating the 1st standard deviation.

4 Conclusion

The influence of fiber length, fiber surface, fiber status, greenbody matrix material, and specimen thickness on the flexural strength and Young’s modulus were studied for short fiber C/Cs. The specimens were measured via a 4 point bending test setup. For the greenbody state, the results of FS and YM show the similar behavior. If the seizing is intact the values are higher than with a thermal decomposed one. No difference between carbonized and graphitized fibers is measurable. The fiber length has no significant influence on the mechanical properties. The resol precursor plate has the lowest FS and YM. For the C/C state no distinct statement for fiber surface and fiber status is

possible. The longer fibers have less mechanical performance as C/Cs. The resin plate delaminated during graphitization. No strong correlation between the greenbody and C/C state was found, which may be an effect of production process fluctuation. A clear result of this study is that the specimen thickness (3 mm or 6 mm) has no impact on the measured FS and YM in greenbody as well as C/C state.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank the SGL Group for supplying the carbon fibers and the production facilities.

The authors gratefully acknowledge the support by the Faculty Graduate Center of Mechanical Engineering of TUM Graduate School at Technical University of Munich, Germany.

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